

THE IMPORTANCE OF RECYCLING NATURAL RESOURCES

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Annotation : Our Republic natural resources efficient use , available of riches without waste technologies based on products work release to the road to put necessary _ Resources ending and endless to groups division account taking , ending i.e unrepeatable resources without waste technologies based on work release enterprises the number increase necessary _

Key words : Resource , exhaustible , oil , gas , ore , coal , technology , reclamation , ecology , global, sustainable , optimization .

Sign in . The increasing number of the population in the world, at the same time, improving the living standards of people, creating conditions for them, and providing them with food products are of great importance. Also, the expansion of the production sector today leads to excessive consumption of available natural resources. This situation worries the population of the world. Research on the rational use of natural resources and their protection in the world, including the use of resource-saving technologies in various sectors of the economy and the protection of biological and landscape diversity, the effective use of water resources in the face of global climate change, the reclamation of irrigated lands special emphasis is placed on research related to improvement.

Today, the experience of developed countries shows that achieving sustainable economic growth is primarily related to the level of effective use of

the available resource potential in the regions.

MATERIAL AND METHODOLOGY

Cartographic, expeditionary, laboratory, systematic and comparative analysis, mathematical-statistical processing of research results based on the problems and solutions of optimization of unfavorable environmental conditions in the natural resources of the Fergana Valley and their use and reproduction, mapping issues and the goals and tasks of the research work a number of methods were used, such as giving, historical-archaeological, systematization and summarization of the obtained data in graphs and tables.

RESULT OBTAINED

Our republic natural conditions peculiar and _ is incomparable . Today's in the day a very large amount of raw mineral resources are mined. Such positive aspects indicate that there are great opportunities in the conditions of economic liberalization. Taking into account the above, first the natural resources of the country and then its natural conditions are evaluated economically.

In the period of the former administration and command, there was insufficient attention to the issues of identifying mineral deposits and their effective use. At that time, our Republic was specialized in growing cotton raw materials. Other sectors were neglected. Today, after gaining independence, our Republic had the opportunity to effectively use underground and surface resources.

"So far, more than 2,700 different mineral deposits and promising places of ore have been identified in Uzbekistan. They include about 100 types of mineral raw materials. More than 60 of these are involved in production. More than 900 mines have been discovered (now about 400 mines, mines, quarries, oil and gas fields are operating on the basis of discovered reserves), their proven reserves amount to 970 billion US dollars. At the same time, the total potential of mineral and raw materials is estimated at more than 3.3 trillion US dollars. Important strategic resources that help to strengthen the country's independence - oil and gas

condensate, 155 promising fields for natural gas, precious metals - More than 40 mines were searched for non-ferrous, rare and radioactive metals, 15 for mining-chemical raw materials.

At the stage of economic liberalization, extraction and processing of mineral raw materials in Uzbekistan occupies one of the leading positions and, in turn, has a positive effect on the development of the economy.

Depending on their use in the national economy, mineral raw resources are divided into: **fuel and energy resources, metal resources** (ferrous, non-ferrous and primary metals), **non-metallic minerals** (mineral and chemical raw materials) **and construction raw materials** .

Fuel energy resources. Uzbekistan has unique fuel and energy resources. discovered gas reserves are about 2 trillion cubic meters, coal - 2 billion, oil - more than 350 million tons. There are more than 160 oil fields. Oil, gas and condensate reserves fully meet the needs of the republic and allow for its export. Today, this area is one of the most effective areas of spending capital.

According to expert research, Uzbekistan has huge oil and gas deposits under the ground. It is possible to single out the regions with oil and gas: **Ustyurt, Bukhara-Khiva, South-West-Khisor, Surkhandarya, Fergana** . The discovered reserves cover the republic's needs for natural gas for more than 35 years, and for oil for up to 30 years.

90 percent of oil more i the most cheap the fountain method is being taken . of Uzbekistan oil and gas mines one how much indicators , such as wells productivity , mining get cost according to next door of regions from mines significant level separate stands _ And this them efficient to work and high benefit to get hope connect _ enable gives _ With that together , that's it oil reserves digging to get expendable additional _ expenses so much a lot because it wo n't oil digging get , prepare and transport for infrastructure set up reach necessity disappears .

Republican gas digging release industry and natural the gas and gas

condensate again work with dependent _ work releases to develop big possibilities there is Most big gas mines **South - west - Hisar _ and Bukhara-Khiva** oil and gaseous in the regions located , these **Shurtan** and **Blessed** groups incoming are mines .

Uzbekistan _ big coal to reserves have _ His geological reserves according to Central in Asia second in place stands _ in Uzbekistan coal **Angren , Shargun** and **Boys** in the mines digging is issued . Theirs common reserve - 2 billion tons . They are between Angren coal _ mine the most unique mine is considered Here _ coal _ reserves advanced as well economic in terms of to the goal according to methods with : 150-250 meters in depth coal layers open method , land under method and land under to the gas rotate method digging is being taken . 2.5 million in Uzbekistan in 2000 tons coal digging received _

Black, non-ferrous, rare and original metals. Reserves of iron, manganese and chrome ores, which belong to the group of ferrous metals, have been discovered in Uzbekistan. According to experts, more than 200 iron deposits are scientifically based. However, it should be noted that there is no opportunity to use these reserves of iron on an industrial basis, but the researches carried out in the regions of the Central Kyzylkum and the lower Amudarya indicate that the opportunities in this regard also have positive characteristics. Prospective reserves of manganese and chromite have been identified in Kashkadarya region and Tomditog and Sultan Uvais mountains.

More than 40 precious metal mines have been discovered in Uzbekistan. Among them, gold is of great importance. In terms of gold reserves, the Republic of Uzbekistan ranks 4th in the world, and in terms of production, it ranks 7th. Many joint ventures are being established in the republic due to the prospect of gold mining. One of them was formed with the participation of the American company "Newmont Maying Corporation" (worth 200 million USD). The fact that this company uses new, modern technologies in its activities has a positive effect. Gold is mined from Muruntov, Ajibugut, Bulutkon, Balpantov, Aristontov,

Torboy, Angren, Chodak, Almalik and similar mines.

CONCLUSION

Rational use of existing medical resources in our country, strengthening of the system of their reproduction. The number of production enterprises should be increased. It is necessary to establish production on the basis of technology without waste from resources. It is necessary to create a mechanism to educate students from primary school that it is the duty of every citizen to use natural resources sparingly.

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